

Hay and Silage Making: An Alternate Source of Quality Fodder for Dairy Farmers

Rahul Banik, Navnit Kumar, Gangadhar Nanda, Sunil Kumar, Barsha Mansingh and Pranjeet Kalita

Abstract

Fodder plays a significant role in livestock farming, it is the main source of amino acids, carbohydrates, proteins, vitamins and minerals with consideration of some anti-nutritional quality factors in sorghum (Nitrate and HCN toxicity) and Lathyrus (BOAA) etc. The choice of fodder depends on several factors, including the nutritional needs of the animals, the availability of land and water resources, and the climate and soil conditions in the area. Fodder can be harvested as hay, silage or fresh forage, and may be supplemented with other feed sources such as grains, minerals and vitamins. Hay and silage are two common methods of preserving forage for livestock feed. Hay is made by cutting and drying grass or legumes, while silage is made by fermenting the forage in an airtight container. Silage, on the other hand, has a higher moisture content and is therefore more prone to spoilage if not properly fermented and stored. However, it can have a higher nutritional content than hay, as the fermentation process can preserve more of the nutrients in the forage.

Introduction

As dairy farming plays an important role in the food supply chain, ensuring a consistent supply of high-quality fodder is critical for dairy farmers. Hay and silage are two commonly used methods of preserving forage for dairy cattle feed. They are rich sources of nutrients and energy that are necessary for the health and productivity of dairy cows. At present, India bears a 512.05 million livestock population and meeting feed and fodder requirements is a questionable issue (19th Livestock Census, 2012). The present availability of green fodder from cultivated areas and pastures is 462.05 million tons

and in the case of dry fodder is 393.88 million tons. By 2020, the demand for green fodder and dry fodder was 1134 million tons and 630 million tons and the supply was 405.9 million tons of green fodder and 473 million tons of dry fodder respectively (IGFRI, 2012).

Due to India's unique climate, substantial feeding issues have been observed during the lean season, when fodder availability is at its lowest. But due to the advancement of science and technology, we can now mitigate the fodder requirement during the lean period (Nov-Jan and May-June). Hay and silage are alternative sources to meet the fodder requ-

Rahul Banik, Barsha Mansingh and Pranjeet Kalita

PG Scholar, Department of Agronomy, Dr. RPCAU, Pusa, Bihar

Navnit Kumar, Gangadhar Nanda and Sunil Kumar

Assistant Professor, Department of Agronomy, Dr. RPCAU, Pusa, Bihar

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Hay as Forage: Hay is a dried form of forage that is often used when fresh forage is not available. The quality of hay depends on several factors such as the plant species, stage of maturity, and environmental conditions. Drying can be performed either naturally (by exposing the forage to the sun on the ground and constantly turning it over to aerate it) or artificially (by the active movement of air). Two to three days must pass without rain for sun-drying. The hay must then be maintained in a suitable environment (covered area). Yet, if the grass is old and has dried out while still standing, it is not hay, it is termed as straw.

Suitable Crops for Hay Making: It is better to make hay from crops with thin stalks and more leaves because they dry out more quickly than those with thick, pitiful stems and few leaves. Oats, desmodium, lucerne, maize, sorghum, napier grass and rhodes grass are a few examples. Leguminous fodder plants (e.g., cowpea, lucerne etc.) should be harvested when crown buds begin to form or when the flowering stage begins.

Procedure of Hay Making: The process of making hay involves several steps, which are essential to ensure the quality of the final product. Here is a general overview of the hay-making procedure:

- ✓ The first step in hay-making is harvesting the forage at the right stage of maturity. Generally, the forage should be harvested when it is at the flowering stage or just before.
- ✓ Once the forage is cut, it needs to be conditioned

to speed up the drying process. This can be done by using a mower conditioner, which crushes the stems and leaves, allowing moisture to escape.

- ✓ After the forage has been conditioned, it is raked into windrows. This helps to expose more of the plant material to the sun and air, allowing it to dry more quickly.
- ✓ The forage needs to be left in the windrows for a few days to dry. This can take anywhere from 1-5 days, depending on weather conditions and the thickness of the windrows.
- ✓ Once the forage is dry, it is baled using a hay baler. There are different types of balers available, including round balers and square balers.
- ✓ Finally, the bales are stored in a dry and well-ventilated area to prevent spoilage (Fig. 1). It's important to stack the bales in such a way that air can circulate around them, which helps to prevent mould and rot.

Fig.1: Hay stored as bales

Factors affecting the quality of Hay: The quality of hay can be affected by several factors. Here are some of the most important ones:

- ✓ The maturity of the crop at the time of harvest is one of the most critical factors affecting hay qual-

ity. Generally, hay harvested at an earlier stage of maturity has higher nutrient content and better digestibility than hay harvested at later stages of maturity.

- ✓ Weather conditions such as rain, high humidity, or prolonged exposure to sunlight can affect the quality of hay.
- ✓ The method of harvesting can also affect hay quality.
- ✓ Proper storage conditions are essential for maintaining hay quality.
- ✓ The type of crop used for hay-making can also affect hay quality. For example, legumes such as alfalfa and clover are generally higher in protein and other nutrients than grasses.

Silage: Silage, on the other hand, is a type of fermented forage made from fresh crops, such as grasses or corn, which are chopped and then stored in airtight containers, such as silos or pits. During the storage period, the chopped crops undergo a natural fermentation process, which preserves the nutrients and extends the shelf life of the feed.

Suitable Crops for Silage Making: There are several crops that can be used for silage making, including maize, alfalfa, clover, sorghum, oats, bajra, napier grass etc. When selecting crops for silage-making, it is important to choose crops that are at the optimal stage of maturity.

Procedure of Silage Making: Proper management of the silage-making process is important for producing high-quality silage that is suitable for livestock feed. The process of making silage involve

several steps:

- ✓ The crops used for silage making should be high in moisture content, have good digestibility, and be free from pests and diseases.
- ✓ The crops are harvested at the optimal stage of maturity, usually when the moisture content is around 60-70%.
- ✓ The crops are chopped into small pieces to increase surface area and aid in the fermentation process.
- ✓ The chopped crops are packed tightly into an airtight container, such as a silo or pit. The packing process removes as much air as possible from the container, creating an anaerobic environment that is necessary for fermentation.
- ✓ The container is sealed to prevent air from entering, which could lead to spoilage.
- ✓ The chopped crops undergo a natural fermentation process, where lactic acid bacteria convert the sugars in the crop to lactic acid, which preserves the nutrients and prevents spoilage.

Fig. 2: Silage

- ✓ After the fermentation process is complete, the

silage can be fed to livestock. Silage is typically fed by removing it from the container and feeding it to livestock immediately, or storing it in a feed bunk for later use.

Additives used for Silage Making: By adding extra sugar or molasses the crop is more able to produce lactic acid. Some additives contain materials to stimulate the lactobacilli bacteria. As the grass is harvested in the field, formic and sulfuric acid are applied at a rate of 3-5 litres per tonne. As a result, less lactic acid is required to achieve a constant pH. Preservatives suppress chemical reactions and allow the fermentation process more easily.

Factors affecting Silage Making: Proper management of the ensiling process, including harvesting, chopping, packing, and storage, is essential for producing high-quality silage that meets the nutritional needs of livestock. There are several factors that can affect the quality of silage, including:

- ✓ The moisture content of the crop at the time of ensiling is a critical factor in the quality of silage.
- ✓ The length of the crop at the time of chopping can affect the quality of silage.
- ✓ The density at which the crop is packed into the silo is an important factor for the quality.
- ✓ Proper fermentation is critical for the quality of silage.
- ✓ The quality of the crop at the time of ensiling can also affect the quality of silage. Crops that are high in moisture, sugar, and other nutrients will generally produce higher quality silage.

Conclusion: Due to the impossibility of expanding

the area used for fodder cultivation, it is determined from the thorough debate that hay and silage are the best alternatives for the stakeholders in the dairy industry. Hay and silage are both important methods of preserving forage crops for use as animal feed. Hay and silage provide essential amino acids and nutrients for the overall development of the animals such as the growth of physical form, milk production, meat etc. Overall, hay and silage are important components of animal nutrition and play a critical role in the sustainability and profitability of livestock production. Proper management of the hay and silage-making process is essential for ensuring high-quality feed and maintaining the health and productivity of livestock.